

Review

Review Study of Teachers and teacher educators' professional development in Ethiopia

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Abstract: *The professional development of teachers and teacher educators is of rising attention worldwide. However, while an increasing range of literature focuses on particular aspects of professional development, there is no integrative reviewed literature that shows the professional development of teacher and teacher educators in Ethiopia. This paper intends to review the related studies on this topic. Thirty-two papers were chosen on basis of exclusion and inclusion criteria to describe, analyse and discuss teacher and teacher educators' professional development in Ethiopia since 1991. The results show the professional development initiatives helped teachers and teacher educators to construct knowledge, skills of doing action research, improve instructional practices and increase professional engagement. However, a low level of use of student-oriented techniques and, as a result, the poor performance of students reported. The findings of this review also highlight a need to reform professional standards for teacher educators. The review suggests more research is needed to show how professional development can contribute to enhancing teacher educator's professional knowledge, skills, and engagement in Ethiopia.*

Keywords: *Continuous professional development, teacher education, teacher educators, professional standards, education in Ethiopia*

Introduction

This integrative review article explores the professional development of teachers and teacher educators and the opportunities that need to learn. The goal of teacher education is to produce effective teachers (Tuli and File 2010). The quality of teacher education is recognized as a significant factor influencing the quality of education and learning outcomes of learners (European Commission 2013). The main goal of teacher training is to qualify future teachers (Koster et al.

2008). To enhance the quality of education, it is necessary to start with the level of teacher educator as a teacher. Teacher educators play a central role in improving the quality of teacher education (Ping, Schellings, and Beijgaard 2018).

Teacher educators are well-defined by the European Commission as anyone who actively coordinates the learning of future teachers (European Commission 2013). This definition includes teacher educators who work in teacher training courses as well as mentors who work mainly in schools (Tack and Vanderlinde 2014). Teacher educators, therefore, play a pivotal role in efforts to enhance the quality of teacher education (Cochran-Smith 2003; Goodwin and Kosnik 2013). A teacher educator is a person who teaches or gives instructions and support to future teachers and thus tries to make a substantial contribution to the development of students into competent teachers (Koster et al. 2008). Professional development of teacher educators can be viewed as a learning continuum, with teacher educators at several points along the continuum (Craig, Kraft, and Plessis 1998). This is necessary because someone who wants to teach others must first be trained. The coexistence of the fact that the improvement of any educational system is an imperative factor to enhance the quality of the teacher educator.

Studies from different countries of the world show that professional development programs are often implemented in teacher education to transform instructional practices (Wabule 2016). The situation means that the need to update and develop the knowledge of teacher educators is competent enough to face the current pressures (Ahmad 2013). Teacher education is therefore part of teacher educators' professional development. Teacher and teacher educator's professional development essentially denotes to the general professional development of an individual. Several researchers have their perspectives and definitions of professional development, such as Glatthorn (1995, 40) states that "the development of teachers is the professional growth achieved by a teacher through the acquisition of more experience and a systematic review of his/her education". The concept of teacher educator's professional development encompasses a broader aspect than career development. It is considered essential to all professional practice. Villegas-Reimers (2003) argues that the professional development of teacher educator is not popular in Ethiopia compared to the professional development of the teacher. However, teacher educator's professional development is a critical factor in the preparation of quality teacher (Robinson and McMillan 2006; Snoek,

Swennen, and Klink 2010). According to Smith (2010) the aim of teacher educator's professional development is quadruple; "enlightening teacher training, meeting external standards, internal drive to learn and improve and strengthening the professional status within higher education" (p.682). She pronounces different paths to teacher educator's professional development that range from formal to non-formal, and individual to the whole staff (Smith 2003). These encompass academic degrees, conferences, lectures and university training in the workplace.

Now a day, a prime issue for teacher education is to offer society with well-equipped teachers to instruct the next generation (Holmqvist 2019). In Ethiopia, learners require differentiated instruction (Ginja 2016; Ginja and Chen 2020a). There is rising attention in Ethiopia in the sector of continuing professional development (henceforth referred to as CPD) to equip teachers. Quality education depends on the scale of teacher [educator]'s CPD (Ministry of Education 2015). CPD is "everything that makes a better teacher, aimed at improving teacher performance in the educational situation of students" (Ministry of Education 2009, 16). Since 2009, CPD for teacher educators has increasingly been seen as an important part of the reform initiative to improve teacher education in Ethiopia. However, little is known about its specific contents, and the delivery process as well as the entire practice. When examining teacher educators' CPD implementation, one has to consider the content of experiences, the processes, and the context in which the professional development take place (Ganser 2000). There are, however, no literature analyses, and no clear route to be followed in a professional development programme of teacher educators in Ethiopia.

This article, therefore, aims to provide a review of literature on the content of teacher educators' professional development and the practices since 1991 in the Ethiopian context. Of all, the questions we intend to answer are: what content is rigorous in CPD frameworks for the teacher training program? How professional development takes place in a teacher training program? And what improvements can be identified in the practices of teacher educators?

Methods

This article does not involve primary data collection and data analysis. Since it does not include the collection and analysis of primary data, using an integrative literature review is the only option (Torraco 2005). This approach of reviewing can be useful if the aim is not to cover all published articles on the topic; and the search strategy is not a systematic (Snyder 2019). The main aim of this study is to review relevant literature in the field of teacher education, the contents of professional development and the practice since 1991 in Ethiopia. In the review, teacher education system, policies and reforms: post-1991, teacher development program, CPD, national professional standards, teacher-education system overhaul, and teacher educators' professional practices were identified as the most significant contents and policy initiatives. In addition, their delivery process discussed under respective sections. For this purpose, a secondary source of data was used. For example, searching was directed by Google Scholar, Web of Science, ERIC and SCOPUS. The main key terms used during searching are teacher education, Ethiopian education, teacher-educator, and continues professional development. The search included published in peer-reviewed scientific journals, country-specific official papers, and related academic and professional publications. Based on the abstracts of the identified articles, we selected a set of 97 articles and policy documents for thorough reading. After reading all 97 articles, and policy documents, a final set of 32 papers were chosen on basis of the same exclusion and selection criteria listed above, 16 original articles, 3 academic studies, and 13 various policy documents.

Results

Teacher education system, policies and reforms in Ethiopia: post-1991

In Ethiopia, the existing teacher education program is intended to improve the quality of teaching at all levels and to address identified gaps in knowledge, execution and involvement of prepared teachers throughout the system (Ministry of Education 2009). After the transitional government of Ethiopia (TGE) came to power in 1991, a new Education policy was introduced in 1994, in which teacher education was identified as one of the priority reform areas. TGE attempted to decentralize the education system in the 11 regions (Chalchisa, n.d.). The current Ethiopian government has recognized the significance of enlightening education as a pivotal to accomplishment for the comprehensive development of the country. This government has published several policies and

reforms to enhance the country's education system. Some important policies and reforms, such as education policy (1994), TESO and TDPs are discussed below.

The new government set new objectives for access, equity, quality and efficiency in the 1994 education policy to restructuring all aspects of the educational provision (Ministry of Education 1994). The policy is aimed at acquiring competence, both at the level of students and teachers in general. It designed to attain four educational goals, namely: quality, access, relevance, and equity specifically. The government has introduced new teacher education colleges and upgrade existing ones, as it believes that to enhance the quality of education, not only the academic qualifications of teachers must be improved, but also the educational institutions that impart the skills. The ethical values of education and the methodological approach of the teachers also need to be improved. Therefore, "teachers must have the skills, dedication, professional interest, and physical and mental fitness appropriate for the profession" (Ministry of Education 2012, 1). The policy highlights new teacher education and training packages with a strong practical focus on all levels of education, so that qualified teachers acquire the necessary skills and an optimistic attitude in applying various methods (Zewdu 2017). The policy statement often emphasizes the use of student-centered approaches, active-learning and problem-solving methods in diverse settings (Serbessa 2006). Therefore, Zewdu (2017) argues that teacher education should model skills and classroom teaching methods that reflect and support education and training policies, as it is a strong advocate of education and training. Teacher education and recruitment policy highlight that

teachers from kindergarten to higher education should have the necessary pedagogical qualifications and skills in educational media, through initial training and further training; and the criteria for the professional development of teachers are continuing education and training, professional ethics and educational achievement (Ministry of Education 1994, 20–21).

After the introduction of the education policy, six years later, Ethiopia confirmed its commitment to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) initiative aimed at increasing access and equity of elementary and senior secondary level education (Ministry of Education 2002). As part of the broader education and training policy, the Ministry of Education has developed a 20-year

Education Sector Development Program (ESDP). The programs focus on the quality of education by focusing on a larger number of qualified teachers and school leaders from 2000 to 2020 (Betemariam 2017; Ministry of Education 1994). Since an introduction of education policy in 1994, the Ethiopian government launched and executed five successive development programs for longitudinal education sectors (ESDP I to V) to improve access, efficiency, equity, quality, and relevance (Frontieri 2019). These programs were aimed at achieving the educational goals of the nation.

Abebe & Woldehana (2013) reported that ESDP I and II considered the scarcity of qualified teachers as one of the key hindrances to the delivery of education. For example, he focused on the expansion of teacher training courses to train primary school teachers through regular, distance and summer education (Abebe and Woldehana 2013). Unfortunately, ESDP I and II have demonstrated poor student performance (Gemeda and Tynjälä 2015). Following this, the Ministry of Education has developed and executed a series of policy guides to address the multilayered difficulties of the education sector. Besides, ESDP III (Ministry of Education 2005) has been launched and given extra priority to the standardization of teacher training approach. Some of the policy documents, such as CPD guide (MoE, 2003); TESO (MoE, 2003); and GEQIP (MoE, 2007), guided the actions. ESDP IV (2010), then, positioned specific emphasis on the enactment of the CPD program. In these efforts, ESDP I, II, III and IV have created opportunities to produce educated and qualified human power (e.g., teachers, teacher educators, students, educational leaders etc.) at all levels (Seyoum 2016). However, evidence indicates that there is a lack of post-graduate teachers. The combination of qualifications of academic staff does not meet the standard set by the Ministry of Education. While the ministry aims at a ratio of 0:70:30 (bachelor, master and doctorate), only a ratio of 27:58:15 has been achieved so far (Ministry of Education 2015). ESDP is now in its fifth planning phase and current priorities include capacity building for better management, improving the quality of general education and access, equality and internal efficiency (World Bank Group 2019). More specifically, the objectives for an existing ESDP V (2015) include improving the quality of teachers, developing essential skills, reducing drop-out and repetition rates, and provision of quality assurance through licensing, scrutinizing school environments, and assessing student accomplishment (Ministry of Education 2015). Despite the progress made in refining equity and access to education, the quality of the education system

continues to worsen, as shown by the outcomes of the national learning evaluations and the assessment of reading in the early years (Frontieri 2019).

Teacher development program in Ethiopia

In 2003, the Ethiopian Ministry of Education led a study into the quality and effectiveness of teachers to find out the weakness of teacher qualification and the system of teaching skills' development. The Ministry of Education introduced the TDP and the CPD Program in 2005, and the revitalization of the professional development framework that followed in 2009 (Betemariam 2017; Desta, Chalchisa, and Lemma 2013; Ministry of Education 2009).

Professional Development in Ethiopia is a national intervention program managed by the Ministry of Education and supported by six European countries to boost the quality and effectiveness of teacher education through initial teacher education. Continuing Teacher Education, TESO, Leadership and Management Program (LAMP) and English Language Improvement Program (ELIP) (Desta, Chalchisa, and Lemma 2013). Besides, the Ministry of Education, in cooperation with these international donors, has advocated two policy initiatives, namely GEQIP I and II to mitigate the falling quality as part of the teacher development program (Joshi and Verspoor 2012). GEQIP aimed to counteract the perceived decline in the quality of education in the country. An important part of this package is the TDP (Akalu 2016). The TDP aims to "boost the quality of teaching and thus the learning of students by strengthening the capacities of teachers in elementary and senior secondary level education" (Ministry of Education 2008, 24).

TDP-I was intended to improve the teacher training methodology system, as well as the knowledge, skills and attitudes of those involved in the teacher education program. TDP initiatives are coordinated by MOE and co-funded by six donor countries (Melesse and Gulie 2019). Instigating a structural transformation in 2003-2004, the TDP-I program was revised and popularly referred to as TDP-II. The functional life of TDP-II has been extended as part of the 8-year GEQIP quality improvement program. Most teacher training and development activities in Ethiopia are combined in the context of the TDP reforms. TDP I and II were launched with important development goals including improving components of TESO, the English Language

Improvement Program (ELIP) and the Leadership and Management Program (LAMP). Desta et al. (2013), and Melesse & Gulie (2019) describe various improvements made in the course of TDP implementation since 2007. However, an exit evaluation of GEQIP II confirms the level of teachers applying student-oriented techniques was low (Frontieri 2019). The TDP guideline has been criticized due to its a top-down approach whereby the interests of faculties and institutions were ignored to share their critical views and concerns (Seyoum 2016). We assume that a top-down approach of TDP contributed to continual domination of teacher-centered approach in the classroom.

The Ministry of Education has recently launched the General Program for Improving the Quality of Equality Education (GEQIP-E), the third phase of World Bank funding and a multi-donor trust fund (Frontieri 2019). The program supports the development of a new strategic framework for teacher training and a new school curriculum for the professional development of teacher/educators (Frontieri 2019).

Continuous Professional Development in Ethiopia

The Ethiopian education policy has long established that the criteria for teacher and teacher educators' professional development are continuing education and training, professional integrity and educational attainment (Ministry of Education 1994). The CPD receives special attention and priority action in education policy.

Figure 1: Series of CPD Programs

The Ministry of Education presented the CPD framework in 2009 as a national response program to meet the transformative needs of education in Ethiopia (Betemariam 2017). The goal of CPD is to enhance teacher performance in the classroom to increase student performance and learning. It is a continuous process aimed at improving knowledge, skills and attitudes towards the local context and in particular classroom practice (Ministry of Education 2009). The overall objective of the CPD program is to enhance student performance at Ethiopian schools and higher education institutions. Villegas-Reimers (2003, 11) specifies objectives of CPD as to:

- support the capacity of teachers to teach effectively employing suitable new student-oriented and problem-solving methods per the active-learning-based program publicized in 1994,
- improve teachers' knowledge of the subject per the content of the curricular materials and pedagogical approaches that require teachers to involve students in the development of higher-order thinking skills,
- help teachers to develop a more positive attitude and a more cooperative approach to their work at school level and to fortify their professional identity,
- introduce the idea of reflective practice and action research through which teachers studied their practice to improve it,

- promote teachers to distinguish their work as a professional by providing new opportunities for growth, investigation, learning and development.

In Ethiopian, CPD is seen as an indispensable approach to progress student achievement by developing the professional skills of teachers and teacher educators by upgrading and updating a wide repertoire of their classroom strategies (Ministry of Education 2009). More specifically, CPD is divided into two categories (Ministry of Education 2009).

Upgrading: the process by which teachers can choose to participate in further studies at appropriate times in their careers; for example, converting a certificate into a diploma, a diploma into a Bachelor degree, the Bachelor degree to a master's degree through regular, summer, evening or distance programs (Ministry of Education 2009). Studies have shown that the CPD framework has helped to 'upgrade' the teacher qualification process, from certification (1-year certification) to diploma (2-year certification), and diploma to Degree levels (4 years and above certificates) (Betemariam 2017). However, concerns expressed about the lack of evidence that the CPD program affected teachers' act (Gemedda and Tynjälä 2015).

Updating: this is a continual process in which every professional teacher participates during his or her teaching career and emphasizes on classroom practice. What we call CPD consists of two components; the first is a two-year induction program for the new teachers, while the second one is for those who are already in the system, where each teacher is expected to complete a minimum of 60 hours CPD time (Ministry of Education 2005). CPD for in-service teachers has four types; induction program, higher diploma program (HDP), ELIP, and appropriate CPD (Ministry of Education 2009). All of these initiatives, including others (see Figure 1), place a substantial emphasis on the teachers and teacher educators' professional development in general. Zeru (n.d., 16) declares the good practices of teacher induction as:

integrated into real classroom experiences. The introductory course is sufficiently organized with a clear vision and objectives. The induction guidelines identify the key stakeholders who should be accountable for the ongoing professional learning and initiation of beginning teachers in the country. The induction program has a

mentoring component and therefore starting teachers can receive mentoring support while they are following the induction course.

On the other hand, the same study reported limitations of induction phases. The induction course is designed at the central level for all starting teachers who join the teaching profession. This stage did not include or apply essential professional training standards to guide mentors and beginning teachers to focus on creating the most important skill to advance teaching and students learning (Zeru, n.d.). Besides, leadership and ownership issues; and weak internal support and lack of external support for teachers identified as a major problem of the teacher training program in Ethiopia (Ministry of Education 2018).

In the current landscape, the participation of teacher [teacher educators] in CPD is connected to their promotion on the career ladder of teachers in five phases (and now in seven phases). The CPD guideline document was intended to provide student-oriented lessons, active and truly engaging learning, by overthrowing traditional teaching methods. Therefore, the CPD document emphasizes the significance of CPD and states that teacher/educators must have access to high-quality professional development. CPD has proven to be effective learning, experience and sharing process and system throughout a teacher's career. All teachers and school principals should have the right to access to quality and relevant opportunities for continuing professional development. The expected outcome for the CPD at work priority area was pedagogical knowledge and enhanced teacher capacities (Melesse and Gulie 2019). It is the civic and professional duty of all teacher educators to engage in CPD (Ministry of Education, 2009). According to the framework, the CPD is a development program that evolves in a cyclical pathway anchored at four phases, namely: Analyse→ Plan→ Do→ Evaluate (Desta, Chalchisa, and Lemma 2013). The first stage of the CPD model, the analysis phase, starts with performing a needs analysis. Personnel must be selected at this stage to identify needs and set priorities according to the given institution. The teacher (educator) must also perform a needs analysis and set priorities accordingly. Once completed, the next planning phase, phase two, requires that the selected staff/faculty member and teachers complete a one-year CPD plan. Following the policy, teachers must follow 60 hours of CPD per year (Ministry of Education 2015). Following these steps, teacher and teacher educators must integrate mandatory courses prepared by the government, combined with programs deemed

necessary by regional management, and any other program from a small menu of CPD courses offered by teacher training institutions.

In the third step, the “Do” step, participants are asked to provide a detailed description of how to take the CPD training. This step requires students to document the steps they took to complete CPD training. The final phase of this CPD model, the evaluation phase, states that all parties will evaluate CPD training (successful or not). During this time, participants are invited to 'assess' each step of this process: they are expected to continuously assess and reflect on their work and student work and record progress in their portfolio (Ministry of Education 2009).

National Professional Standards for Ethiopian School Teachers

Professional development standards and frameworks have been advanced worldwide since the 1990s by various educational jurisdictions and professional organizations (Broad and Evans 2006). Most professional development standards are included in broader professional practice frameworks. The Ethiopian ministry of education has defined seven national standards for teachers (Ministry of Education 2012). The standards for teachers indicate what is expected from teachers in three educational domains. The demonstration of the standards by the teacher will take place in his or her particular educational context at his or her stages of expertise and will reflect the learning needs of the students he teaches. The standards are grouped into three areas of education; expertise, professional practice and professional commitment.

Table 1: National professional standards

Standard	Domain
1 Know learners and how they learn	professional knowledge
2 Know the content and how to instruct it	
3 Plan for and implement effective instruction	professional practice
4 Create and maintain supportive and safe learning environments	
5 Assess, provide feedback and report on student learning	
6 Engage in professional learning	professional engagement
7 Engage professionally with colleagues, parents/caregivers and the community	

Source: Continuous Professional Development for Primary and Secondary School Teachers, Leaders, and Supervisors in Ethiopia: The Practical Toolkit (Ministry of Education 2009)

Teacher Education System Overhaul (TESO) Program

A few years later, after the instigation of the education policy of 1994, the Ministry of Education led a study into the quality and effectiveness of teacher education in Ethiopia. Based on the result, a policy framework called TESO was launched in 2003 to develop the objectives and strategies of the teacher's education. TESO focuses on five priority programs with an emphasis on teacher recruitment, training, and education. It also stresses school-based and learner-centered learning in pre-and in-service training of teacher, hands-on training and preparation for the teaching profession. TESO aims to close the pedagogical knowledge gap and improve the quality of teacher preparation in Ethiopian teacher training courses. The program is designed to "solve serious problems in the education system" (Ministry of Education 2003, 6). It is expected that active learning methods will be used in teacher training and that continuous evaluation will be implemented. TESO was aimed to address these problems and improve the quality of teacher preparation. Mekonnen (2008, 285) stated the research findings pointed out by the evaluation task force regarding teacher training system are:

the professional competence of the teachers is insufficient, the knowledge of the content of the teachers is insufficient, the teachers do not meet the standards and expectations of their profession, the internship receives insufficient attention and is poorly performed, the quality of the courses and teaching methods are academic and teacher-oriented, and there is a lack of professionalism and ethical values in Ethiopian teacher education.

Teacher Educators Professional development in Ethiopia

Teacher [and teacher educators'] professional development is increasingly seen as an important element of reform initiatives to improve teacher education in Ethiopia (Akalu 2016). Teacher educators' professional developments in different higher institutions are set to accomplish two major targets: to improve the professional skills of academic staff and to support academic programs to maintain the quality of student learning (HERQA 2006). The professional quality of a teacher educator contains diverse skills and competencies that necessitate specific training for

mastery. Teacher educators at all institutional levels are now required to follow a CPD program (Ministry of Education 2015). Among teacher educators' professional development programs commenced the HDP, and the ELIP are most recognized.

A course entitled the HDP is being offered to teacher-educators working in colleges and universities (Tessema 2006). The program began in 2003 as a recommendation of the study conducted by the task force. It is a responsive action to the call for quality teacher training in higher institutions (Gebru 2016). The pivotal goal of the HDP is to develop the skills of teacher educators in areas of action research, active learning, reflective teaching and continuous assessment. As the program objectives detailed (Gebru 2016, 3): help teacher educators

- identify their own needs and become reflective teacher-educators;
- develop teaching as a skill, based on solid theoretical knowledge and solid experience;
- use active learning and differentiated instruction;
- be participated in the research, in particular, action research;
- build teamwork skills; and
- plan teacher-educator professional development.

Over the past decade, HDP becomes essential to advance the professional competencies of teacher educators and to boost the quality of instruction. It was created to enhance the quality of training provided by developing the skills and professionalization of teacher educators (Gebru 2016). The aim was to address the recognized needs of teacher-educators and to support the execution of the TESO program. Moreover, the HDP is a kind of continues in-service training program to create a reflective teacher and improve the standards of teaching and learning in the country (Gebru 2016). The HDP comprises of mostly adult attendants and instigates them to memories, replicate, and perform the country's directives and rigid instructional principles. It transfers the knowledge and technical skills necessary for teacher educators to contribute to classroom practices. The HDP has shown a promising impact on addressing the gap related to pedagogical knowledge of the teachers and has been successfully implemented so far (Ahmad 2013). However, there are communal and academic matters that the early career academics (ECAs)) program is not helping them to better

perform their responsibilities (Gebru 2016). As studies show, the HDP is the only institutionalized mode of a professional development scheme. The following includes some major observations of the study conducted by Gebru (2016, 11–12):

- The HDP intends to improve the quality of higher education in general and the perception and practice of ECAs in particular. However, there is a lack of localization of material resources in the existing country context and its tradition.
- Since no local academics were involved in the development of the HDP, ECAs may think this was a politically imposed and donor-driven program, and therefore universities, including ECAs, may be reluctant to take over it.
- The course layout doesn't take into account the differences in participants profiles. Nevertheless, it has not put in place mechanisms to monitor the practical execution of the program in the classroom proper or its contribution to the implementation of ECAs in teaching and research.
- The program lacks relevance to the program, for example, knowledge of subject matter and its application.
- Ownership of HDP is not localized and thus may lack sustainability. It may thus be concluded that the course has so far not lived up to anticipation in helping ECAs to effectively discharge responsibilities of teaching and research in particular and to conduct them to the profession in general.
- The course is not localized and therefore cannot be sustainable.

Besides, the Ethiopian government decided that English training would be part of the education reform. An ambitious project called ELIP was started in 2003 with an already initiated goal when the Ministry of Education developed a policy to advance the level of teachers' English language skill. ELIP emphasized on boosting the English language and the pedagogical skills of teacher educators. ELIP has had a tremendous effect on the professional development of teachers across the country. ELIP has become a priority package of a wider teacher development program, a vital element in reaching the third phase of the country's ESDP (Ahmad 2013).

Discussion

The Ethiopian government has made a foremost exertion to transform society and help the country to become a lower-middle-income economy by 2030. In recent years, the economy has grown at nearly 10% per year, one of the fastest growth rates in the world. In this period, particular consideration was paid to renovating the economic and social set-up and encouraging pro-poor spending on education, health, and other services to support the poor and the marginalized. 'Education is a significant indicator reflecting the level of a nation's development (Cam Tosun 2018, 407) whereas teacher educators are the force behind all such developments. Because of this crucial role, the education sector has experienced a series of successive and continuous development programs for the education sector. The teacher development program is a continuous process, not an event. The teacher development program is an ongoing process, not an event. From the moment teachers begin preparation or initial instruction, arrangements must take place for the continued development of their subject knowledge; practical skills for teaching, observing, evaluating and reflecting; incentives; and career development (Craig, Kraft, and Plessis 1998).

This study presents a review of teacher and teacher educators' professional standards in Ethiopia since 1994. The findings from this an integrative literature review of the policy documents highlight some of the significant actions. This review presents an overview of the content of professional learning, the learning activities that teacher educators undertake and the reasons for professional development. For example, the Ministry of Education has developed series of programs such as Education sector development program (2000 – 2020), Teacher development program (2003 – to date), Continues professional development (2009 – to date), GEQIP I (2009 - 2013), GEQIP II (2013 -2018), and GEQIP-E (2018 – to date) within the broader framework of education policy. The programs focus on the quality of education by focusing on a larger number of qualified teachers and school leaders at all levels, standardization of teacher education programmes, and providing equitable access to education.

Changes in a country's education system demands call for staff development activities (Ginja and Chen 2020b). The professional values for teacher educators were established collaboratively led by the Ministry of Education, involving central level officials, and international supporters. However, less attention was given for regional level expertise, teacher education institutions,

employers and teacher unions (Gemechu et al. 2017). The professional standards have provided a framework for teacher professionalism under three domains such as teacher professional knowledge, practice, and engagement. These domains constitute seven professional standards. This review confirmed that being a professional teacher or teacher educator in Ethiopia has come to be connected with possessing the set of standards (Akalu 2016).

Findings suggest that even if there are considerable improvements have been achieved, still, poor student performance demonstrated, and teacher-oriented techniques of teaching used. The fifth ESDP yet intended to mitigate the persisting gaps of professional standard for teacher and teacher educators through enhancing the quality of training, and provision of quality assurance through licensing, examining school environments, and assessing educational attainment. To complement ESDPs, the Ministry of Education has advocated other important policy initiatives, namely the GEQIP I, II and GEQIP-E to mitigate the falling teacher education quality.

To attain the objective of teacher training, diverse approaches to teacher training have been executed worldwide in the teacher training system around the globe (Sasson, Kalir, and Malkinson 2020). The finding showed that some programs such as TESO, practicum, HDP, and ELIP are closely related to teacher educators in Ethiopia. TESO was introduced by task forces to address issues of quality and effectiveness of teacher education focusing on programs such as recruitment, training, and education of teachers (Gemechu et al. 2017). A commencement of practicum in the teacher education system was the most valuable part of the education system in Ethiopia (Tuli and File 2010), which provides a strong foundation for effective professionalism of teachers (MoE, 2003). Practicum is a significant point in the process of teacher training (Huong et al. 2020). Likewise, analysis connected with HDP revealed the following major findings:

- HDP helped teacher educators to understand more about higher education in a globalized world,
- despite teacher educators' initial doubt about the importance of higher Diploma Program (Pedagogy), the respondents asserted that it helped them improve their pedagogical competences,

- the professional development training helped teacher educators' also construct knowledge in the areas of curriculum development in general and in the use of the modular approach in particular,
- the HDP enhanced teacher educators' skills of doing action research,
- the HDP opened up teacher educators' interest for further professional development training, and
- the HDP helped teacher educators' share experiences among colleagues and improve their interpersonal skills

The review suggests that the adjustment of the HDP manual should take place with the instantaneous outcome, including the reorganization of content based on needs assessment, the selection of leaders and teachers through modelling of good practice and monitoring and evaluation strategies (Gebru 2016).

As revealed in this study, official reports show that significant improvement has been made in teacher and teacher educators' professional development succeeding the new education and training policy (Ministry of Education 2015). Achievements include the decentralization in the teacher development program to somehow that has empowered regional governments to lead teacher training colleges that produce teachers for primary schools; and to recruiting, hiring, promoting and transferring teachers; and make CPD for the teacher (educator) one of the priorities of teacher development exertions at the various levels of the education system (Ministry of Education 2015; 2018). Based on the findings, an evolving model of teacher educators' professional development is illustrated as follow (figure 2).

Figure 2: Evolved Model for Teacher educator's professional development

On the contrary, the study conducted by Anto (2006) quoted in Seyoum (2016), indicates that a large number of teacher educators are not curious to participate in highly relevant university professional development activities. The lack of pedagogical competencies of the teacher educators, lack of commitment from management and some academic staff, lack of transparent leadership, and resources to perform activities were some of the shortcomings of CPD training (Seyoum 2016).

Furthermore, findings from this review refer to the policy recommendation forwarded by “Ethiopian education development roadmap (2018-30)” (Ministry of Education 2018, 45), show that there is a need to

- re-conceptualize the CPD to fill in the gaps, both in the knowledge of the subject matter and in the pedagogical skills needed to teach specific content.
- develop relevant and high-quality materials/modules to support teacher (educator)s' learning.
- integrate the CPD into the career structure of teachers and granting licenses.
- reform (vice versa) the current system where teachers get higher after gaining higher qualifications through upgrading.

Conclusion

Quality of teacher training determines the quality of teachers and educators, thereby the quality of students, further leading to the overall development of nations (Chen 2013; Ginja and Chen 2020a). This review discussed numerous key points from Ethiopian teacher education and educators' professional standards that may improve the deal regarding the ways to become a professional in the field of teaching. The major findings highlight:

- CPD is seen as an educational leadership alternative to improve educational attainment by developing teachers and teacher educators' professional (Ministry of Education, 2009). A CPD framework acknowledges the necessity of active learning methods (e.g., Abebe & Woldehana, 2013; Akalu, 2016). Correspondingly, it calls upon the participation of various stakeholders for its effective implementation (Akalu 2016; Gemeda and Tynjälä 2015). However, the functionality and contribution of CPD were inconsistently found.
- the HDP significantly contributed to the enhancement of the pedagogical competences, and this conclusion consistent across research articles (eg., Wirtu, 2019).
- the practicum program is also a highly valued component of the teacher training program that aim to equip teachers who are thoughtful, reflective and inquiring (e.g., Tuli & File, 2010).

The results of this review suggest that there is a need to put in place an effective and functional system of professional development of teacher educators which is as per the need of the profession. The educational authorities, policymakers, and other regulatory body need to work continuously to develop and refine proof of experience, utility and quality of professional development.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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